

Ammonite fauna and biostratigraphy of the Jurassic in Sierra de Reyes (Mendoza, Argentina)

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Abstract: The biostratigraphically important ammonitina of Sierra de Reyes, southernmost Mendoza province, eastern margin of the central part of the Neuquén Basin are identified and key taxa are illustrated. Sierra de Reyes is a north-south oriented brachyanticline, with a nucleus of Upper Triassic-Lower Jurassic volcanics and continental beds, and Middle-Upper Jurassic marine strata at its western and eastern limbs. Three and five sections were studied on the western and eastern slopes, respectively, and 79 fossiliferous localities were sampled. A succession of 16 bio- and chronostratigraphic units was identified, spanning the interval from the Aalenian to the Oxfordian, resting on top of Upper Triassic-Lower Jurassic volcanics and continental beds and capped by the gypsum of the Auquilco Formation. Most of these zones are widely recognized in the southern Andes. The zonation is as follows: 1: *Bredya manflasensis* Assemblage Zone, Lower to Middle Aalenian; 2: *Westermanniceras groeberi* Assemblage Zone, Middle Aalenian; 3: Malarguensis Standard Zone, Upper Aalenian to Lower Bajocian; 4: Singularis Standard Zone, lower Lower Bajocian; 5: Giebeli Standard Zone, middle Lower Bajocian; 6: Humphriesianum Standard Chronozone, upper Lower Bajocian; 7: Rotundum Standard Chronozone, Lower Upper Bajocian; 8-10: *Morphoceras gulisanoi* Assemblage Zone; 9: Cadomites-Tulitidae mixed assemblage, (? Lower-) Middle, and Upper Bathonian; 10: Steinmanni Standard Zone Uppermost Bathonian, with one local horizon: Stehnocephalites gerthi horizon; 11: Vergarensis Zone, Bathonian Callovian boundary; 12: Bodenbenderi Zone, Lower Callovian; 13: Proximum Standard Zone, uppermost Lower Callovian; 14: Rehmannia patagoniensis Horizon, Middle Callovian; 15: *Peltoceratoides* – *Parawedekindia* Assemblage Zone, Upper Callovian-Lower Oxfordian; 16: *Perisphinctes-Araucanites* Assemblage Zone, upper Lower and Middle Oxfordian.

Keywords: Jurassic, Aalenian-Oxfordian, ammonites, west-central Argentina.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sierra de Reyes is located (Fig. 1) in southernmost Mendoza province, east of río Colorado, slightly south of the confluence of the Grande and Barrancas rivers. The area is on the eastern margin of the central part of the Neuquén Basin.

Since the works of Groeber (1918, 1929, 1933) and Groeber *et al.* (1953) the Sierra de Reyes region became a classic area of the Andean Middle Jurassic. According to Groeber (1918, p. 7) the best Andean Middle Jurassic succession is exposed in that area. Since then the succession was studied and fossils collected in 1984 by C. Gulisano, leading a team of geologists of YPF (the State Oil Agency) within a programme to study the Jurassic of the Neuquén Basin. The biostratigraphic information was summarized by Riccardi & Westermann (1991a). Later Spalletti *et al.* (2012) studied some material from

four fossiliferous levels collected in two sections of the western slope, three of them in Quebrada Remoredo, and one in La Estrechura (cf. Fig. 1).

Sierra de Reyes is a north-south oriented brachyanticline, with a nucleus of Upper Triassic-Lower Jurassic volcanics and continental beds, and Middle-Upper Jurassic marine strata as its western and eastern limbs (Fig. 1). The marine Middle Jurassic is developed with its maximum thickness in the less accessible western slope of the Sierra. There, three sections were studied and collected by Gulisano and Gutiérrez Pleimling in 1984, from south to north La Estrechura, Quebrada Remoredo and Quebrada de la Buitrera. Other sections along the eastern slope of Sierra de Reyes are, from south to north, Agua de la Mula, studied by Riccardi, Uliana, Damborenea and Manceñido, Cañada Honda and Agua del Campo, studied by Groeber (1918, 1929, 1933; Groeber *et al.*, 1953, see also Stipanovic *et al.*, 1976), Agua del Ñaco studied

Fig. 1. Geological map of the Sierra de Reyes region, (Modified) from Groeber, 1933; Holmberg, 1976; Narciso *et al.*, 2004; with sections described and mentioned in text: 1, La Estrechura; 2, Quebrada Remoredo; 3, Quebrada La Buitrera; 4, Cañada Honda; 5, Agua del Ñaco; 6, Agua de Reyes; 7, Agua de la Mula, 8, Agua del Campo.

by Gulisano in 1984, Agua de Reyes, studied by R.A. Pombo in 1978 and by Gulisano and Gutiérrez Pleimling in 1984.

The Middle Jurassic to Oxfordian fossiliferous succession rests on top of the continental beds of the Remoredo Formation (Triassic-Lower Jurassic). It includes in its lower part the Cuyo Group, with the whitish sandstones and shales of the Bardas Blancas Formation, the gray to black shales of the Los Molles Formation (Aalenian-Bajocian), the yellowish-gray and greenish sandstones and shales of the Lajas Formation (Bathonian-Callovian). Above are the dark-gray shales with interbedded limestones of the Lotena Formation (Callovian-Oxfordian), the grayish limestones of the La Manga Formation (Oxfordian) and the gypsum of the Auquilco Formation (Oxfordian).

On the western slope (Figs 1, 2) the most complete section, c. 315 m thick, is in Quebrada Remoredo, where the

Bardas Blancas Formation is 40 m thick, the Los Molles Formation 190 m thick, the Lajas Formation 60 m thick and the Lotena and La Manga formations respectively 15 and 5 m thick. In La Estrechura and La Buitrera only the Los Molles and the Lajas formations are present, with 70 and 60 m and 120 and 13 m respectively.

On the eastern slope (Figs 1, 2) the most complete section appears to be at Agua de Reyes with a total thickness of c. 285 m of which 240 m are represented by the Bardas Blancas Formation. In the different sections the Los Molles Formation is c. 10-25 m thick, the Lajas Formation between c. 10 and 30 m, the Lotena Formation between 15 and 30 m, and La Manga Formation between 5 and 15 m.

The seven stratigraphic sections depicted in Fig. 2 are based on sections made by C. Gulisano and Gutiérrez Pleimling, excepting Agua de la Mula, which was studied by A. Riccardi, M. Uliana *et al.* in 1982. The different

Fig. 2. Main sections in Sierra de Reyes described in text, from south to north, western slope: La Estrechura, Quebrada Remoredo, La Buitrera; eastern slope: Agua del Naco, Agua de Reyes, Agua de la Mula.

biostratigraphic units indicated by encircled numbers refer to the units mentioned in the explanation of that figure.

2. AGE AND AFFINITIES OF AMMONITE ASSEMBLAGES, BIOZONES AND STANDARD ZONES

The biostratigraphy of the Middle Jurassic of Argentina has been dealt with, totally or in part, in Westermann & Riccardi (1972, 1973, 1979, 1985), Riccardi (1984, 2008a, b), Riccardi & Westermann (1984, 1991a, b), Hillebrandt & Westermann (1985), Riccardi *et al.* (1991, 1994, 2000), Hillebrandt *et al.* (1992), Dietze *et al.* (2010, 2012) and Parent (2022). Below is a biostratigraphic summary of the Sierra de Reyes region (Fig. 3), which mostly follows that summarized by Riccardi (2008a, b) for the whole Neuquén basin.

In classifying the Andean successions on the basis of their ammonites, it was possible to distinguish three levels of stratigraphic units according to how widely their characteristic faunas are recognizable (cf. Riccardi *et al.*, 1989a, b, c). In this classification and in its application to the Jurassic of the area we have followed the rules and criteria established in the International Stratigraphic Guide (Hedberg, 1976; Salvador, 1994), and the Argentinean Stratigraphic Code (Riccardi *et al.*, 1992). Here, it must be remarked that it is not accepted the idea that the use of the complete name of the index species is unnecessary and inconvenient, leading to misinterpretations (cf. Parent, 2022, p. 3). On the contrary, it is considered here that what can be confusing is to restrict the name to the specific epithet.

At the lowest level is the **faunal horizon**, a term used to describe a bed or range of beds in a section characterized by a particular species after which the horizon is named, within which no further stratigraphic differentiation of the fauna can be distinguished. It may be stratigraphically recognized at only a single locality, although its characteristic species may have been also found elsewhere. It may be separated from adjacent faunal horizons by unfossiliferous intervals or non/sequences, recognized or only suspected. It may have been found at

STAGES	STANDARD ZONES	SIERRA DE REYES
OXFORDIAN	M	TRANSVERSARIUM
		PLICATILIS
	L	CORDATUM
		MARIAE
CALLOVIAN	U	LAMBERTI
		ATHLETA
	M	CORONATUM
		JASON
	L	GRACILIS / CALLOVIENSE
		BULLATUS
BATHONIAN	U	DISCUS
		RETROCOSTATUM
	M	BREMERI
		MORRISI
		SUBCONTRACTUS
		PROGRACILIS
	L	AURIGERUS
		ZIGZAG
BAJOCIAN	U	PARKINSONI
		GARANTIANA
		NIORTENSE
	L	HUMPHRIESIANUM
		PROPINQUANS
		LAEVIUSCULA
DISCITES		
AALENIAN	U	CONCAVUM
	M	MURCHISONAE
	L	OPALINUM

Fig. 3. Correlation of the Sierra de Reyes Jurassic ammonite assemblages and zones with the standard chronostratigraphic scale.

several localities, in which case a time/correlation may, but need not necessarily, be assumed. An example is the *Stehnocephalites gerthi* horizon described below. At the next level are stratigraphic intervals characterized

Plate I

Figs 1-2. *Bredya delicata* Westermann, lateral and ventral views of an incomplete phragmocone (MLP 17051), bed G1109, La Estrechura.

Figs 3-4. *Bredya delicata* West., Ventral and lateral views, incomplete phragmocone (MLP 10991), Agua de la Mula. loose, c. level M213.

Figs 5-7. *Podagrosiceras athleticum* Maubeuge & Lambert, macroconch with incomplete body chamber (MLP12817), lateral and ventral views, Agua de la Mula, bed M213.

All figures natural size

by **faunal assemblages**, some or all of whose members are more widely recognizable, and which may therefore be correlatable over some distances even if approximately. They will in general again be separated by gaps of unknown duration. Their status is that of biozones (assemblage zones) and they are labelled by the name of one of their characteristic faunal elements, usually an ammonite genus or species. An example is the *Megaspherocheras rotundum* assemblage zone. There are also “mixed” assemblages in which there is an admixture of faunas of different ages, which may have been caused by reworking. Such a case is present at Chacay Melehue where a Middle-Upper Bathonian Cadomites-Tulitidae Mixed Assemblage was defined (Riccardi *et al.*, 1989a, b, c, 1990a).

At the third level of classification lies the scale of **standard chronostratigraphy**. Such a scale consists of a succession of contiguous chronostratigraphic zones bounded, and hence defined, by time/planes. To distinguish biozones from standard chronozones, the names of the latter are written in Roman script. The characteristic faunas can be recognized from Mexico to the southern Andes. Most of them cannot be closely correlated with the standard succession of Europe because of strong faunal provincialism. The scale is therefore a bioprovincial secondary standard, Andean scale, ranging from the Aalenian to the Oxfordian in the primary standard.

Aalenian (pars lowermost Bajocian)

1. *Bredyia manflasensis* Assemblage Zone. Introduced by Hillebrandt & Westermann (1985), is poorly represented in west-central Argentina (see Riccardi *et al.*, 1990a, 2000; Riccardi, 2000, 2008a, b). Early to Middle Aalenian, Opalinum and Early Murchisonae Zone.

In Sierra de Reyes is present on its southwestern slope, at La Estrechura and Quebrada Remoredo, where is c. 40 m thick, with *Bredyia cf. delicata* Westermann (Pl. I, figs 3-4) and *Planammatoceras* sp. In La Estrechura it is within the lower part of the Los Molles Formation, whilst in Quebrada Remoredo it is within the Bardas Blancas Formation, which in both localities rests on top of the Remoredo Formation (Fig. 2).

The zone is not present farther north at La Buitrera, nor

in the sections exposed on the eastern slope of Sierra de Reyes.

2. *Westermanniceras groeberi* Assemblage Zone. Introduced by Westermann & Riccardi (1979, see Riccardi *et al.*, 1990a, 2000; Riccardi, 2000, 2008a, b), it is present throughout west-central Argentina. Middle Aalenian, Murchisonae Zone.

In Sierra de Reyes (cf. Fig. 2) is represented with *W. groeberi* (West. & Ricc.) (Pl. II, figs 1-2), *Planammatoceras planinsigne* (Vacek) (Pl. II, fig. 5, Pl. III, figs 1-3) and *Tmetoceras* ex gr. *scissum* (Benecke) (Pl. II, figs 3-4) and it is present in all studied sections within the Los Molles Formation, excepting Agua del Ñaco. In the eastern slope of Sierra de Reyes, at Agua de la Mula and Agua de Reyes, it is close to the contact with the Remoredo Formation, whilst on the western slope, at La Estrechura and Quebrada Remoredo, it is 35 to 50 m above the top of that formation.

3. *Malarguensis* Standard Zone was introduced by Westermann & Riccardi (1979, see Riccardi *et al.*, 1990a, 2000; Hillebrandt *et al.*, 1992; Dietze *et al.*, 2010). It is widespread in west-central Argentina, and includes (cf. Hillebrandt & Westermann, 1985), from below, the biosubzones of *Puchenquia compressa*, *P. mendozana* and the *Podagrosiceras maubeugei* Horizon/Subzone, Late Aalenian to earliest Bajocian, Concavum to Early Discites Zones. In Sierra de Reyes it is 30-40 m thick and it is represented by *Puchenquia (P.) malarguensis* (Burck.), *P. (Gerthiceras) mendozana* West. and Ricc., *P. (G.) compressa* West. & Ricc. (Pl. III, figs 4-5), *Planammatoceras* sp., *Csernyeiceras moerickei* (Jaw.), *Euhoploceras amosi* West. & Ricc., *Podagrosiceras athleticum* Maub. & Lamb. (Pl. I, figs 5-7). It is present in Los Molles Formation, at 72 to 78 m above base in La Estrechura, c 55 m above base in Quebrada Remoredo, 10 m above base in La Buitrera and in Agua de la Mula, and 30-85 m above base of the Bardas Blancas Formation in Agua de Reyes (cf. Fig. 2).

Bajocian

4. *Singularis* Standard Zone. Introduced by Westermann & Riccardi (1979) is widespread in west-

Plate II

Figs 1-2. *Westermanniceras groeberi* (West. & Ricc.), almost complete body chamber (MLP 17068), lateral and ventral views, La Estrechura, bed G1150.

Figs 3-4. *Tmetoceras* ex gr. *scissum* (Benecke), complete phragmocone with incomplete body chamber (MLP 10993). Ventral and lateral views. Agua de la Mula, bed M212.

Fig. 5. *Planammatoceras planinsigne* (Vacek), phragmocone with almost complete body chamber (MLP 17047). Lateral view. La Estrechura, bed G1109.

All figures natural size

central Argentina. Early Bajocian, Late Discites and Early Laeviuscula Zones. The regional Bajocian stratotype was defined (Westerman & Riccardi, 1989) at the base of this zone at Cerro Puchenque, Mendoza province. Within this zone two subzones were recognized by Dietze *et al.* (2010), i.e. the *Sonninia zitteli* Subzone and the *Sonninia altecostata* Subzone.

In Sierra de Reyes (Fig. 2) is c. 10-40 m thick and is represented by *S. zitteli* (Gottsche) (Pl. IV, figs 1-2), *Sonninia cf. altecostata* Tornq. (Pl. IV, fig. 7), *Pseudotoites cf. sphaeroceroides* (Tornquist). On the western slope is within the Los Molles Formation, about 80-100 above the base in Quebrada Remoredo and about 50-60 above the covered base in La Buitrera. On the eastern slope is present within the Bardas Blancas Formation, at 70-80 m above base in Agua de la Mula.

5. Giebeli Standard Zone. Introduced by Westermann & Riccardi (1979) is widespread in west-central Argentina, it includes, from below, the Subzones of *Emileia submicrostoma* and *E. multiformis*, and the *Dorsetensia blancoensis* Horizon/Subzone. Early Bajocian, Late Laeviuscula and Propinquans Zones.

In Sierra de Reyes with *E. multiformis* (Gott.) (Pl. IV, figs 8-9), *E. (Chondromileia) giebeli* (Gott.) (Pl. IV, figs 5-6), *Sonninia (P.) espinazitensis* Tornq. (Pl. IV, figs 3-4), *Sonninia aff. alsatica* (Haug) (Pl. V, figs 1-2), *Witchellia* sp., *Dorsetensia aff. edouardiana* (d'Orbigny), *D. mendozai* West. & Ricc., *D. blancoensis* West. & Ricc. (Pl. VI, figs 5-6). On the western slope (Fig. 2) is present within the Los Molles Formation at 120-145 m above base in Quebrada Remoredo and about 70-80 m above the covered base in La Buitrera. On the eastern slope (Fig. 2) is present within the Lajas Formation at 102 m above base in Agua de la Mula and at 160-230 m above base of the Bardas Blancas Formation in Agua de Reyes.

6. Humphriesianum Standard Chronozone. The originally European standard zone was extended to northern Chile (Westermann & Riccardi, 1979; Riccardi *et al.*, 1990a, 2000) where it includes, from below, the Subzones of *Dorsetensia romani* and *Duashnoceras chilense*. It is rare in west-central Argentina.

In Sierra de Reyes it is represented with *Stephanoceras*

sp. (Pl. VI, figs 7-8), *S. (S.) pyritosum* (Qu.), *S. (Stemmatoceras) cf. allani* (Warren) (Pl. VI, figs 3-4), *Sphaeroceras (Defonticeras) cf. defontii* (McLearn).

On the western slope (Fig. 2) it is present within the Los Molles Formation at c. 170 m above base in Quebrada Remoredo and is probably represented by c. 30 m unfossiliferous levels in La Buitrera. On the eastern slope (Fig. 2) it is present within the Bardas Blancas Formation, at 130-150 m above base in Agua de la Mula and at 240 m above base in Agua de Reyes.

7. Rotundum Standard Chronozone. It was introduced for North America (Hall & Westermann, 1980), was recognized in the Andes by Westermann & Riccardi (1979; see Riccardi *et al.*, 1990a, 2000), it is rare in west-central Argentina. In Cordillera Domeyko, Chile, a subzone, i.e. the *Lupherites dehmi* Subzone, was differentiated in its lower lower part by Westermann & Riccardi (1979, pp. 111-112). Later (Parent, 2022, p. 13) the name of the zonal index was used for the upper part of this zone, despite the fact that the Argentine Code of Stratigraphy (Riccardi *et al.*, 1992, p. 35) and the International Stratigraphic Guide (Salvador, 1994, p. 66) stated that “the same name should not be used for different biostratigraphic units of the same kind, even of different rank”.

In Sierra de Reyes it is represented with *Megasphaeroceras magnum* Ricc. & West. (Pl. VII, figs 1-2). On the western slope (Fig. 2) it is present within the Los Molles Formation at c. 190 m above base in Quebrada Remoredo and 10 m below top in La Buitrera. It has not been found on the eastern slope.

Bathonian

8-10. Morphoceras gulisanoi Assemblage Zone (Riccardi & Westermann, 1999), **Cadomites-Tulitidae Mixed Assemblage** (Riccardi *et al.*, 1989a), **Steinmanni Standard Zone** (Riccardi *et al.*, 1988) (cf. Riccardi *et al.*, 2000), are typically developed, the first at Agua del Ñaco, on the eastern slope of Sierra de Reyes (c. 37° S, 69° 45' W), and the other two at Chacay Melehue, Neuquén province. Early to Late Bathonian.

It should be noted that it has been proposed (Parent *et al.*, 2020) the division of the *Lilloettia steinmanni* Zone

Plate III

Fig. 1. *Planammatoceras planinsigne* (Vacek), phragmocone with almost complete body chamber (MLP 17047). Ventral view. La Estrechura, bed G1109.

Figs 2-3. *Planammatoceras planinsigne* (Vacek), almost complete phragmocone (MLP 17069). Lateral and ventral views. La Estrechura, bed G1150.

Figs 4-5. *Puchenquia (Gerthiceras) comporessa* West. & Ricc., incomplete phragmocone (MLP 17074). Lateral and ventral views. La Estrechura, bed G1155.

All figures natural size

into two subzones, i.e. the *Steinmani* Subzone and the *Gerthi* Subzone, despite the fact that, as noted above, the Argentine Code of Stratigraphy (Riccardi *et al.*, 1992, p. 35) and the International Stratigraphic Guide (Salvador, 1994, p. 66) rule otherwise.

In Agua del Ñaco, Sierra de Reyes (Fig. 2) at the base of the Lajas Formation there is a level showing a mixing of the three different assemblages recognized (see Riccardi, 2008a, p. 330) for the Andean Bathonian, characterized by *Morphoceras gulisanoi* Ricc. & West. (Pl. VIII, figs 1-6), *Procerites* cf. *schloenbachi* (de Grossouvre) (Pl. X, figs 1-2), *Oxycerites* cf. *aspidoides* (Oppel) (Pl. VII, figs 3-4), *Lilloettia steinmanni* (Spath) (cf. Pl. XI, figs 3-4), *Iniskinites gulisanoi* Ricc. & West. (Pl. IX, figs 1-3), *Iniskinites* sp. nov. A, *Eurycephalites* sp., ?*Xenocephalites neuquensis* (Stehn) (G1557) and *Choffatia* sp. (cf. Pl. IX, figs 7-8). A level 3 m higher provided *Stehnocephalites gerthi* (Stehn) (cf. Pl. XI, figs 1-2).

Callovian

11. Vergarensis Standard Zone. Defined by Riccardi *et al.* (1988) it is typically represented in Chacay Melehue, Neuquén province (cf. Riccardi *et al.*, 1990a, 1994) and it is characterized by *Eurycephalites vergarensis* (Burck.), *Neuquenicerias (N.) steinmanni* Stehn, and *Xenocephalites gottschei* (Tornq.). Earliest Callovian.

The regional Callovian stratotype was defined (Westermann & Riccardi, 1989) at the base of this zone at Chacay Melehue.

In Sierra de Reyes (Fig. 2) it is probably present with *Neuquenicerias* sp., ?*Eurycephalites* sp. and *Eurycephalites* indet. on the western and eastern slopes, respectively at Quebrada de la Buitrera and Agua del Ñaco, 10-15 m below the top of the Lajas Formation.

The alleged inclusion of *E. vergarensis* and *X. gottschei* in a single dimorphic pair and a change in the name of this zone (see Parent, 1998, 2022), is questionable, as raw data were not given, relationships between macro- and microconch phragmocones are not evident, stratigraphic ranges differ for both species, and material from type localities was not considered (cf. Riccardi, 2008a, b; Westermann, in Westermann *et al.*, 2002, p. 509).

12. Bodenbenderi Standard Zone. Originally defined at Chacay Melehue, Neuquén province by Riccardi *et al.* (1988, 1989a), Early Callovian, latest Bullatus and Gracilis Zones.

In Sierra de Reyes (Fig. 2) is 20 m, 25 m and 5 m below top of the Lajas Formation, respectively at Quebrada La Buitrera, Quebrada Remoredo and Agua del Ñaco, and is characterized by *Neuquenicerias* cf. *steinmanni* Stehn (Pl. XI, figs 5-6) and *Eurycephalites* sp. (Pl. IX, figs 3-6).

13. Proximum Standard Zone. Defined at Chacay Melehue (Riccardi *et al.*, 1989a), with *Hecticoceras (H.) proximum* Elmi, *H. (H.)* cf. *hecticum* (Rein.), *H. (H.) boginense* (Pet.), *H. (Chanasia) navense* Román, *H. (Ch.) ardescicum* Elmi, *Xenocephalites stipanicici* Ricc. *et al.*, *X. involutus* Ricc. & West., *Neuquenicerias (Frickites)* cf. *antipodum* (Gott.), *Rehmannia (R.)* cf. *paucicostata* (Tornq.), *R. (R.) brancoi* (Stein.), *R. (R.) stehni* (Zeiss), *Oxycerites (Paroxycerites) oxynotus* (Leanza). Early Callovian, late Gracilis Zone.

Thus far no representatives of this zone have been found in Sierra de Reyes, although in the Quebrada Remoredo section (Fig. 2) there is a 30 m unfossiliferous succession above levels referred to the Bodenbenderi Standard Zone that could well be equivalent to the Proximum Standard Zone.

14. Rehmannia patagoniensis Horizon. Defined by Riccardi & Westermann (1991b; cf. Riccardi, 2008b), with abundant *R. (Loczyceras) patagoniensis* (Weaver) (Pl. XII, figs 1-2), typically represented in near-shore facies along the eastern margin of the Neuquén Basin. Middle Callovian, Jason and Coronatum Zones.

In Sierra de Reyes (Fig. 2) it is present close to the base of the Lotena Formation in the western slope, at Quebrada Remoredo and in the eastern slope, at Agua de la Mula, Agua del Ñaco and Agua de Reyes.

Oxfordian (pars uppermost Callovian)

Marine Oxfordian is well represented in west-central Argentina, although with a relatively poorly preserved ammonite fauna (see Riccardi *et al.*, 1990b), mostly

Plate IV

Figs 1-2. *Sonninia zitteli* (Gottsche), incomplete phragmocone (MLP 17022), lateral and ventral views. Quebrada Remoredo, bed G1137.

Figs 3-4. *Sonninia espinazitensis* Tornquist, incomplete body chamber (MLP 17078), lateral and ventral views. La Estrechura, bed G1156.

Figs 5-6. *Emileia (Chondromileia) giebeli* (Gottsche), phragmocone with incomplete body chamber (MLP 16975), lateral and ventral views, Quebrada Remoredo, bed G1122 (loose).

Fig. 7. *Sonninia* cf. *altecostata* Tornquist, incomplete phragmocone (MLP 12851), lateral view, Agua de la Mula, bed M217.

Figs 8-9. *Emileia multiformis* (Gottsche), almost complete phragmocone with part of body chamber attached on opposite side (MLP 16984), ventral and lateral views, Quebrada Remoredo, bed G1127.

All figures natural size

restricted to Middle Oxfordian levels of La Manga Formation.

Late Callovian - Early Oxfordian and Late Oxfordian faunas are not usually present, due to regional hiatus, or are geographically restricted and poorly preserved. This situation and frequent absence of precise information on stratigraphic precedence has hindered most attempts to refine the Late Callovian-Oxfordian stratigraphy (cf. Parent, 2006, 2022), and supports restriction in the use of zonal names to those of regional significance, leaving aside those applied to isolated faunal levels of which there is no evidence in Sierra de Reyes.

15. *Peltoceratoides* – *Parawedekindia* Assemblage Zone. Defined in Riccardi *et al.* (1990b). As “*P. pressulus* Biozone” in Parent (2006; Parent & Garrido, 2015), is present (unpublished) in the western part of the Neuquén Basin, with *Peltoceratoides* sp. and *Parawedekindia* sp., although there is no evidence of its presence in Sierra de Reyes. Latest Callovian - Early Oxfordian, latest Lamberti to Early Cordatum Zones.

16. *Perisphinctes-Araucanites* Assemblage Zone. This assemblage (Riccardi *et al.*, 1990b) is widespread throughout the Neuquén Basin, and is equivalent to the “*Subvinalesphinctes pseudokranaus*, *Passendorferia* and *Euaspidoceras tarapacaense* Biozones” of Parent (2006). Latest Early and Middle Oxfordian, Latest Cordatum to Transversarium (?and Bifurcatum) Zones.

In Sierra de Reyes is present on the western slope in Quebrada Remoredo and on the eastern slope in Agua del Ñaco, Agua de la Mula and Agua de Reyes. It is characterized by *Perisphinctes* (*Kranaosphinctes*) spp., *P. (Dichotomoceras)* cf. *wartae* Bukowski (Pl. XII, figs 3-4), *P. (Arisphinctes)* spp. (Pl. XIII, figs 2-3), *Araucanites stipanicici* West. & Ricc. (Pl. XIII, figs 4-5), *Euaspidoceras* aff. *waageni* Spath (Pl. XII, fig. 5, Pl. XIII, fig. 1).

3. NOTES ON THE AMMONITE FAUNAS

The stratigraphic occurrences of representatives of the different taxa in the studied sections are mentioned, with indication of the numbers assigned to them in the Museo de la Plata (MLP) collections. For the figured specimens

traditional measurements (DM = Maximum diameter; DU = Umbilical diameter; H: Height of whorl section; W= width of whorl section) are also included.

Family Hildoceratoidea Hyatt, 1867

Tmetoceras ex gr. *scissum* (Benecke)

Pl. II, figs 3-4

For a synonymy of this species see Westermann (1964a, p. 428) and Westermann & Riccardi (1972, p. 22, pl. 1, figs 1-5).

The species was found at the base of the marine Jurassic, immediately above continental beds of the Remoredo Formation, in Agua de la Mula, bed M212 (MLP 10993, Pl. II, figs 3-4; DM= 31, UD= 13.7, H= 10, W= c. 6.8) and Agua de Reyes, bed M3, on the eastern slope of Sierra de Reyes.

Family Hammatoceratoidea Buckman, 1887

Subfamily Hammatoceratinae Buckman, 1887

Bredyia delicata Westermann

Pl. I, figs 1-4

Species originally described and figured by Westermann (in Hillebrandt & Westermann, 1985, p. 28, pl. 5, figs 1-4; pl. 6, fig. 1, text fig. 10c; MLP 17051 refigured here Pl. I, figs 1-2).

The species is well represented on the western and eastern slope of Sierra de Reyes at La Estrechura, bed G1109 (MLP 17051, Pl. I, figs 1-2; DM= c. 116, UD= 21.4, H=c. 58.3, W= 40.1; MLP 17049, 17052, 17054, 17059) and Agua de la Mula, bed M213 (MLP 10991, Pl. I, figs 3-4; DM= 30.8, UD= 7.7, H= 14, W= 12.3).

Planammatoceras planinsigne (Vacek)

Pl. II, fig. 5; Pl. III, figs 1-3

This species, discussed by Westermann (1969, pp. 65, 69, 71) and Westermann & Riccardi (1982, pp. 18-23), is well represented at la Estrechura, bed G1109, western slope of Sierra de Reyes, and the two specimens here figured (MLP 17047; Pl. II, fig. 1; Pl. III, fig. 1; DM= 185, UD= 67.3, H= 68.8, W= 40; and MLP 17069; Pl. III, figs 2-3; DM= ?108; UD= 334.4, H= 45.7, W= 27) are a close match of the lectotype figured by Vacek (1886, pl. 13, fig. 1; refigured in Westermann & Riccardi,

Plate V

Figs 1-2. *Sonninia* aff. *alsatica* (Haug), Phragmocone with incomplete body chamber (MLP 13975), lateral and ventral views, Agua de Reyes, bed s/n.

Figs 3-5. *Emileia* gr. *brocchii* (Sowerby), complete specimen (MLP 13980), apertural, lateral and ventral views, Agua de Reyes. Bed s/n.

All figures natural size

1982, text-fig. 3). A specimen from the same locality and horizon, previously identified by Spalletti *et al.* (2012, p. 472, fig. 5B) as *Planammatoceras* sp. appears to be more involute and has different ribbing but its poor preservation precludes any closer comparison.

Puchenquia (Gerthiceras) compressa
Westermann & Riccardi
 Pl. III, figs 4-5

The genus/subgenus and species was discussed by Westermann & Riccardi (1982, pp. 32-36) and in Sierra de Reyes is represented at La Estrechura, bed G 1155 (MLP 17074; Pl. III, figs 4-5; DM= 75, UD= 21, H= 33.7, W=* 16.9), and Agua de Reyes, bed M7 (MLP 14041). The species *P.(G) mendozana* is probably present in Quebrada Remoredo, bed G1116 (MLP 16968)

***Podagrosiceras athleticum* Maubeuge & Lambert**
 Pl. I, figs 5-7

A complete synonym of this species is in Riccardi, 2000, p. 18, and the specimen here figured is from Level M213, Agua de la Mula (MLP 12817, DM= c. 84.8, UD= 33, H= c. 31, W= 28); it was originally figured by Westermann & Riccardi (1979, p. 116, pl. 1, figs 1a-c, fig. 5).

The specimen from La Estrechura identified by Spalletti *et al.* (2012, p. 472, fig. 5C) as *Podagrosiceras* cf. *athleticum* albeit its poor preservation could well be a microconch of this species as those figured by Westermann & Riccardi (1979, pl. 1, figs 3-4).

***Westermanniceras groeberi* (Westermann & Riccardi)**
 Pl. II, figs 1-2

This species was originally described by Westermann & Riccardi (1972, p. 94, pl. 31, figs 1-5) on the basis of material from several localities of Mendoza province (i.e. Bardas Blancas, arroyo Blanco and Las Yeseras) and assigned to the genus *Zurcheria* Douvillé. Since then the species was reviewed by Riccardi (2000, p. 24, pl. 1, figs 7-10) on the basis of material from different localities from the Aconcagua-Neuquén Basin, from southern

Neuquén province to southern San Juan province and designated as type of the genus *Westermanniceras*. In Sierra de Reyes has been found on the western slope, at La Estrechura, bed G1150, MLP 17068, (Pl. II, figs 1-2; DM= 48, UD= 18.6, H= 18.2, W= 16.4).

Family Sonniniidae Buckman, 1892
***Sonninia zitteli* (Gottsche)**
 Pl. IV, figs 1-2

The species originally described by Gottsche (1878) was discussed at length by Westermann & Riccardi (1972, pp. 59-72) and in Sierra de Reyes has only been recorded in Quebrada Remoredo, bed G1137, with an incomplete phragmocone (MLP 17022; Pl. IV, figs 1-2; DM= 58.5, UD= 11.8, H= 30.4, W= 17.7), which as the species has a relatively involute and narrow umbilicus, and an elliptical whorl section with almost smooth flanks and a complex suture.

***Sonninia espinazitensis* Tornquist**
 Pl. IV, figs 3-4

The species was discussed at length by Westermann & Riccardi (1972, pp. 77-92) and in Sierra de Reyes is present in most studied localities along the western (La Estrechura, bed G1156, MLP 17078, here figured in Pl. IV, figs 3-4, DM= 79.5 mm, UD= 733 mm, H= 33.6 mm, W= +15 mm; Quebrada Remoredo, beds G1122 (MLP 16978), 1124 (MLP 16981), 1126 (MLP16985), Quebrada de La Buitrera, bed G1185 (MLP 19414-6) and eastern slopes (Agua de la Mula M219-220, Agua de Reyes, bed M9 (MLP14043), bed M10 (MLP 14044), bed G1206 (MLP 20089, 20091-2), Agua del Campo.

***Sonninia* cf. *altecostata* Tornquist**
 Pl. IV, fig. 7

This species, included by Westermann & Riccardi (1972, pp. 77, 83) as a possible chronological older subspecies of *S. espinazitensis* has since then been separated (cf. Hillebrandt, 2001, pp. 56, 58; Dietze *et al.*, 2010, pp. 91-95; 2021, p. 29) as a distinct species. Probably present

Plate VI

Figs 1-2. *Dorsetensia blancoensis* Westermann & Riccardi, almost complete specimen (MLP 13981), lateral and ventral views, Agua de Reyes.

Figs 3-4. *Stephanoceras (Stemmatoceras)* cf. *allani* (Warren), incomplete phragmocone (MLP 16999), lateral and ventral views, Quebrada Remoredo, bed G1132.

Figs 5-6. *Dorsetensia blancoensis* Westermann & Riccardi, incomplete phragmocone (MLP 16993), lateral and ventral views, Quebrada Remoredo, bed G1129.

Figs 7-8. *Stephanoceras* sp., incomplete phragmocone (MLP 20075), lateral and ventral views, Agua del Ñaco, bed G1218.
 All figures natural size

in Agua de la Mula, bed M217 (MLP 12851, here Pl. IV fig. 7, DM= 35.3 mm, UD= 11 mm, H= 13.8 mm, W= ? 8 mm).

***Sonninia alsatica* (Haug)**

Pl. V, figs 1-2

The species was discussed by Westermann & Riccardi (1972, pp. 48-51) and has been recorded in Quebrada La Buitrera, Quebrada Remoredo and Agua de Reyes. One specimen (MLP 13975) from Agua de Reyes (here figured on Pl. V, figs 1-2, DM= 87.6 mm, UD= 35.1 mm, H= 30.8 mm, W= 18.8 mm) compares well with the specimen from a similar level of Quebrada Remoredo figured by Spalletti *et al.*, 2012, fig. 5A as “*Dumortieria cf. pusilla*”.

***Dorsetensia blancoensis* Westermann & Riccardi**

Pl. VI, figs 1-2, 5-6

The genus and species were discussed by Westermann & Riccardi (1972, pp. 101-102) and are now recorded with an incomplete phragmocone [MLP 16993; DM= 75.3 mm, UD= 26.5 mm, H= 30 mm, W= 18 mm] in Quebrada Remoredo, bed G1129, and almost complete specimen (MLP 13981, DM= 108.3 mm, UD= 39.4 mm, H= 39.3 mm, W= +21 mm) in Agua de Reyes.

Super Family Haploceratoidea Zittel, 1884

Family Oppeliidae Bonarelli, 1894

***Oxyerites (Oxyerites) cf. aspidoides* (Oppel)**

Pl. VII, figs 3-4

Specimen collected from bed G1219, Agua del Ñaco (MLP 20046), where it was found in association with *Morphoceras gulisanoi* and *Procerites cf. schloenbachi* described, figured and discussed previously by Riccardi & Westermann (1999, p. 202, fig. 4A-B). x 0.91

Super Family Stephanoceratoidea Neumayr, 1875

Family Stephanoceratidae Neumayr, 1875

***Stephanoceras* sp.**

Pl. VI, figs 7-8

Representatives of the genus *Stephanoceras* Waagen, 1869, are present in several localities along the western

(Quebrada Remoredo) and eastern slopes (Agua de la Mula, beds M220-221, Agua del Ñaco, bed G1218, Agua de Reyes, bed G1209) of Sierra de Reyes. A specimen from Agua de la Mula highest level M221 (MLP 12855) resembles *Stephanoceras pyritosum* (Quenstedt) a species previously described from the Andes by Westermann & Riccardi (1972, p. 155, pl. 21, figs 1-3). The specimen here figured (MLP 20075, DM ?75 mm, UD= ?29.8 mm, H= 24.4 mm, W= +18.3 mm) comes from bed G1218, Agua del Ñaco.

***Stephanoceras (Stemmatoceras) cf. allani* (Warren)**

Pl. VI, figs 3-4

Material from the Andes was previously compared with this species of Warren (1947) by Westermann & Riccardi (1979, p. 168), and has now has been recorded in Quebrada Remoredo, bed G1132 (MLP16999, DM= 65.5 mm, UD= 28.6 mm, H= 22.3 mm, W= 36.5 mm).

Family Otoitidae Mascke, 1907

***Emileia (Emileia) multiformis* Gottsche**

Pl. IV, figs 8-9

The genus/subgenus and species were discussed at length by Westermann & Riccardi (1979, pp. 119-126), and are well represented in Sierra de Reyes at La Estrechura and Quebrada Remoredo. The specimen from Quebrada Remoredo figured here (MLP 16984; Pl. IV, figs 8-9; DM= 59.3, UD= 7.5, H= c. 34.5, W= ?41.9) is a phragmocone which half of body chamber preserved on one side.

***Emileia (Chondromileia) giebeli* (Gottsche)**

Pl. IV, figs 5-6

The subgenus and species were discussed at length by Westermann & Riccardi (1979, pp. 129-134) and are represented at ?La Buitrera (MLP 19417), Quebrada Remoredo and Agua de Reyes (MLP 14045). The specimen from Quebrada Remoredo figured here (MLP 16975, Pl. IV, figs 5-6) has an incomplete and distorted body chamber (DM= ?71.2, UD= ?12.2, H= 36.3, W= c. 30).

Plate VII

Figs 1-2. *Megasphaeroceras magnum* Riccardi & Westermann, incomplete phragmocone (MLP 19433), lateral and ventral views. Quebrada de la Buitrera, bed G1188.

Figs 3-4. *Oxyerites (Oxyerites) cf. aspidoides* (Oppel), incomplete phragmocone (MLP 20046), lateral and ventral views, Agua del Ñaco, beds G1219, 1557.

All figures natural size (reproduced at a different scale in Parent, 2022, fig. 10E).

***Emileia ex gr. brocchii* (Sowerby)**

Pl. V, figs 3-5

The specimen (MLP 13980) from an unknown level of Agua de Reyes, here compared with Sowerby's (cf. 1827, pl. 710a, b) species compares well with one previously described by Westermann & Riccardi (1972, p. 126, pl. 2, figs 2a-b, DM= 104.4 mm, UD= 42.3 mm, H= 42.2 mm, W= 52.4 mm) and also differs from *E. brocchii* in the more widely and spaced, broader secondaries.

Family Sphaeroceratidae S. Buckman, 1920***Megasphaeroceras magnum* Riccardi & Westermann**

Pl. VII, figs 1-2

The genus and species have been discussed at length by Riccardi & Westermann (1991a, pp. 90-96). Present on the western slope of Sierra de Reyes, in La Buitrera, bed G 1188 (MLP 19433-4; the specimen here figured has the following measurements DM= 61.4 mm, UD= 5.1 mm, H= 8.37 mm, W= 8,35 mm).

***Lilloettia steinmanni* (Spath)**

Pl. XI, figs 3-4

The genus and species has been discussed by Riccardi & Westermann (1991a, pp. 52-58) and in Sierra de Reyes have been recorded in La Estrechura, bed G 1157 (MLP 17086) and Agua del Ñaco, bed G 1557 (MLP 20053).

***Iniskinites gulisanoi* Riccardi & Westermann**

Pl. IX, figs 1-2

The genus and species were discussed by Riccardi & Westermann (1991a, pp. 61-63, 66-68), and is represented at La Estrechura, bed G1157. One specimen, MLP 17082 here refigured in Pl. IX, figs 1-2, is an almost complete specimen (DM= 80 mm, UD= 5.6 mm, H= 43.6 mm, W= 35 mm). The species is highly distinct in comparison to other Andean and Northamerican species by its compression and ribbing.

***Eurycephalites* sp.**

Pl. IX, figs 3-6

Two specimens from bed G1160, La Estrechura (MLP 17093a-b, figs 3-4, DM= 42 mm, UD= c. 8, H=27.2 mm,

W= 29.5 mm) have similar involute coiling, ribbing and whorls section as juveniles or inner whorls of some representatives of *Eurycephalites*, as figured by Riccardi & Westermann (1991a, pl. 1, figs 3a-4b, 6a-b, pl. 2, figs 4a-b, pl. 3, fig. 5a-b).

***Stehnocephalites gerthi* (Stehn)**

Pl. XI, figs 1-2

The species was discussed at length by Riccardi & Westermann (1991a, pp. 82-88). It is present at La Estrechura, bed G1158 (MLP 17092), Quebrada Remoredo, beds G 1136-7(MLP 17005-6), and Agua del Ñaco, bed 1158 (MLP20058-9, 60). Material from then same level of Quebrada Remoredo was also figured by Spalletti *et al.* (2012, figs 6A and 6D-E).

***Araucanites* spp.**

Three different species of *Araucanites* are present in Sierra de Reyes, as described by Westermann & Riccardi (in Stipanovic *et al.*, 1976), i.e. *A. stipanovici* (MLP 12240, bed G1213, Agua de Reyes, here refigured in Pl. XIII, figs 4-5), *A. reyesi* (MLP 12241) and *A. mulai* (MLP 12247), the last two from beds M224-227, Agua de la Mula. The genus has also been reported from Chacay Melehue and northern Chile (cf. Parent, 2006, p. 50, figs 45A-B) with material ascribed to a new species, although the Chacay Melehue material (figs 456A-B) probably belongs in a different genus and clearly differs from the northern Chile material figured by Hillebrandt & Gröschke (1995, pl. 6, figs 1-4).

Superfamily Perisphinctoidea Steinmann, 1890**Family Morphoceratidae Hyatt, 1900*****Morphoceras gulisanoi* Riccardi & Westermann**

Pl. VIII, figs 1-6

The species was introduced by Riccardi & Westermann (1999, p. 196, pl. 1, figs 1-6, pl. 2, figs 1-5, figs 2-3A-B; here refigured) for material collected in Agua del Ñaco, beds G 1557 and G1219 (MLP 20043, DM= 109.5 mm, UD= 45.2 mm, H= 32.6 mm, W= 26.8 mm; and MLP 20047, DM= 83 mm, UD=28.9 mm, H=28.5 mm, W= 21.7 mm). Main features and differences with other species were discussed there.

Plate VIII

Figs 1-3. *Morphoceras gulisanoi* Riccardi & Westermann, holotype, almost complete specimen (MLP 20043), lateral, ventral and apertural views, Agua del Ñaco, bed G1219, G1557.

Figs 4-6. *Morphoceras gulisanoi* Riccardi & Westermann, paratype, almost complete specimen (MLP 20047), lateral, ventral and apertural views, Agua del Ñaco, bed G1219, G1557.

All figures natural size (figs 3-6 reproduced by Parent, 2022 at a different scale).

Family Reineckeidae Hyatt, 1900***Rehmannia (Loczyceras) patagoniensis (Weaver)***

Pl. XII, figs 1-2

This species has been described and discussed by Riccardi & Westermann (1991b, pp. 125-129). It has been recorded along the eastern slope of the Andes, from southern Neuquén to Mendoza provinces. In Sierra de Reyes has been found in Cañada Honda, Quebrada Remoredo, bed G1139 (MLP 17009-17010), Agua del Ñaco, bed G 1562 (MLP 20065), Agua de la Mula, bed M 222 (MLP 23984-6), and Agua de Reyes, beds M13 (MLP 14047), G1213 (MLP 19578-82).

Neuqueniceras cf. steinmanni Stehn

Pl. XI, figs 5-6

Representatives of this species are probably present in bed G1138, Quebrada Remoredo (MLP 17008, Pl. XI, figs 5-6) and Quebrada de La Buitrera, bed G1196 (MLP 19436).

Family Perisphinctidae Steinmann, 1890***Choffatia cf. aequalis (Roemer)***

Pl. IX, figs 7-8

A specimen of *Choffatia* (MLP 17087, DM= 64.5 mm, UD= 26.5 mm, H= 23 mm, W= + 20.8 mm) from La Estrechura, bed G1157 was found together with an upper Bathonian assemblage belonging to the *Lilloettia steinmanni* Zone. It resembles the specimen figured by Riccardi *et al.* (1989a, p. 569, pl. 2, figs 6-7) which was also compared with the holotype of this species, coming from the upper Retrocostatum Zone of northwest Germany. The specimen is also similar to those figured by Mangold (1970, pl. 2, figs 9-11) coming from levels of similar age.

Perisphinctes (Dichotomoceras) sp.

Pl. XII, figs 3-4

The Andean Oxfordian is characterized by a large number of perisphinctids, which have usually been included in the genera/subgenera *Perisphinctes* Waagen, *Arisphinctes* and *Kranaosphinctes* Buckman gen., and

are usually correlated with the uppermost Cordatum to Transversarium Standard Zones. But they have not been studied in any detail. Only a few papers described and figured some specimens (Steinmann, 1881; Stehn, 1923; Leanza, 1947a, b; Stipanovic, 1951; Covacevich, 1982, 1984; Gygi & Hillebrandt, 1991; Parent *et al.*, 2006).

The specimen here figured (MLP 13346; Pl. XII, figs 3-4) may well be referred to *Perisphinctes (Dichotomoceras)* and resembles *P. (D.) warte* (Bukowski.) (cf. Bukowski, 1887, p. 140, pl. 27, figs 1a-c; Enay, 1966, p. 486, pl. 30, figs 1-2; Melendez, 1989, p. 296, pl. 43, figs 1-2, pl. 44, figs 1-2; Glowniak, 2006, fig. Ta-b; Glowniak & Wierzbowski, 2007, p. 93, fig. 55).

Perisphinctes (Arisphinctes) sp.

Pl. XIII, figs 2-3

The specimen here figured (MLP 17018), from bed G1140, Quebrada Remoredo is representative of a number of poorly preserved specimens coming from the Oxfordian of Sierra de Reyes. This material compares well with the specimens from Arroyo de la Manga figured by Stipanovic (1951, pl. 1, fig. 3, pl. 2, fig. 2, pl. 3, fig. 2) ascribed to the same genus and subgenus and compared with *P. (A.) cotovui* Simionescu (cf. Arkell, 1939, pl. 24, figs 1-5, pl. 25, figs 1; and *P. (A.) helenae* de Riaz (cf. Arkell, 1939, pl. 30, figs 7-8, pl. 31, figs 1-3, fig. 48; Enay, 1966, pl. 20, figs 1-4).

Procerites cf. schloenbachi (de Grossouvre)

Pl. X, figs 1-2

Two specimens (MLP 20040, 20052) were previously studied by Riccardi & Westermann (1999, p. 200, pl. 3, figs 1-2) and compared with *P. schloenbachi* de Grossouvre as figured by Arkell (1958, p. 171, Fig. 62, 2a-c) and Sturani (1967, p. 30, pl. 14, figs 2a, b). They came from bed G1219, Agua del Naco, where they are associated with other Bathonian species such as *Lilloettia steinmanni* (Spath), *Iniskinites gulisanoi* Riccardi & Westermann, *Oxyerites cf. aspidoides* (Oppel), and *Morphoceras gulisanoi* Ricc. & West.

Plate IX

Figs 1-2. *Iniskinites gulisanoi* Riccardi & Westermann, almost complete specimen (MLP 17082), lateral and ventral views, La Estrechura, bed G1157.

Figs 3-6. *Eurycephalites* sp., incomplete phragmocones (MLP17093), lateral and ventral views, La Estrechura, bed G1159, 1160.

Figs 7-8. *Choffatia cf. aequalis* (Roemer), incomplete phragmocone (MLP 17087), lateral and ventral views, La Estrechura, bed G1157.

All figures natural size

Family Aspidoceratidae Zittel, 1895***Euspidoceras* aff. *waageni* Spath**

Pl. XII, fig. 5, Pl. XIII, fig. 1

The species *E. waageni* was introduced by Spath (1931, p. 599, pl. 115, fig. 7) for a specimen from Cutch originally described by Waagen (1875, p. 91, pl. 16, fig. 4) as “*Aspidoceras perarmatum*”. The species is characterized by a subquadratic whorl section with flat to slightly curved flanks and venter and umbilical and ventrolateral tubercles.

Material compared with the species was figured by Jeannet (1951, p. 217, pl. 103, fig. 1) from Herznach, Switzerland.

The specimen here figured (MLP 13345; DM= 88.00 mm, UD= 34.5 mm, H= 33.3 mm, W= 35.4 mm; Pl. XII, fig. 5, Pl. XIII, fig. 1) is from the Oxfordian of Agua de la Mula, bed M227. To the same species is also comparable the incomplete phragmocone from Quebrada Remoredo (MLP 17016) included by Parent (2006, p. 31) in a poorly defined new species.

4. FOSSIL LOCALITIES**4.1. Sierra de Reyes (36°45' – 37° S, 69°38' – 46 W)****1. La Estrechura**

This section north of 37° S and the one exposed slightly to the north in Quebrada Remoredo are probably the same from which Groeber (1918, pp. 7-12; 1933, pp. 10-11) mentioned levels with ammonites indicating Aalenian, Bajocian and Callovian followed by the “Yeso Principal”. Groeber mentioned that the section was continuous and that the apparent absence of Upper Bajocian and Bathonian ammonites did not attest to the absence of levels of those ages.

The same section was studied by Gulisano and Gutiérrez Pleimling and the collected ammonites, studied by Riccardi & Westermann (1991a), indicated Aalenian, Bajocian, Bathonian, Callovian and Oxfordian. Gulisano divided his section in two parts, part I (from the top of the Remoredo Formation to the lower third of the Cuyo Group (Bardas Blancas Formation and lower part of Los Molles Formation), part II covered the upper part of the Los Molles Formation and part of Lajas Formation. About 150 m between parts I and II were not measured.

The fossiliferous succession is as follows (numbers of fossil samples as in Fig. 1):

- c. 60 m yellowish-gray and greenish sandstones and shales (Lajas Formation). Several fossiliferous levels:
 - c. 20-21 m below top beds G1159, 1160 with: *Xenocephalites neuquensis*, (MLP 17090, *X.* sp. (MLP 17091), *Eurycephalites* sp. (MLP 17093). Bodenbenderi Zone.
 - c. 50 m below top bed G1158 with: *Stehnocephalites gerthi* (MLP 17092). Gerthi Horizon.
 - c. 53 m below top bed G1157 with: *Iniskinites gulisanoi* (MLP 17082), *I.* n. sp. (MLP 17084), *Lilloettia steinmanni* (MLP 17086), *Xenocephalites* cf. *neuquensis*, (MLP 17085), *Choffatia* sp. (MLP 17087), *Oxycerites* sp. (MLP 17088, 20046, 9, 50). From this level probably came the specimen identified as “*Iniskinites* cf. *crassus*” in Spalletti *et al.* (2012, fig. 2B). Steinmanni Zone.
- 80 m Dark-gray shales and sandstones (Los Molles Formation).
 - c. 76-80 m above base, loose from bed G1156 with: *Puchenquia malarguensis* (MLP 17076), *Sonninia espinazitensis* (MLP 17078, 9), *Emileia* sp. (MLP 17073).
 - 78 m above base bed G1155: ?*Puchenquia* (*Gerthicerias*) *mendozaana* (MLP 17074), *Planammatoceras* sp. (MLP 17075). Malarguensis Zone. From this level or from the one below came the specimens identified as “*Planammatoceras* sp.” and “*Morphoceras* sp.” in Spalletti *et al.* (2012, fig. 5B, 5D).
 - 72 m above base bed G1154: *Planammatoceras* (*Pseudaptetoceras*) sp. (MLP 17070). Malarguensis Zone.
 - 35 m above base bed G1150: *Planammatoceras* cf. *planinsigne* (MLP 17050, 65, 67, 69), *Westermanniceras groeberi* (MLP 17068). Groeberi Zone. From this level probably came the specimen identified as “*Podagrosiceras* cf. *athleticum*” in Spalletti *et al.*, 2012, fig. 1C.
 - 23,5 m above base bed G1148: *Planammatoceras* sp. (MLP 17064), *Bredyia* sp. (MLP 17062). Manflasensis Zone.
 - 16 m above base bed G1147: *Planammatoceras* sp. (MLP 17063).
 - 14 m above base bed G1146: ?*Planammatoceras* sp.
 - 12 m above base bed G1145: *Bredyia* sp.
 - c. 8-9 m above base bed G1142-3: *Bredyia* cf. *manflasensis* (MLP 17060, 1).

Plate X

Figs 1-2. *Procerites* cf. *schloenbachi* (de Grossouvre), incomplete specimen (MLP 20052), lateral and ventral views, Agua del Ñaco, bed G 1219, 1557.

Figs 3-4. *Oxycerites*? sp., incomplete phragmocone (MLP 20049), lateral and ventral views, Agua del Ñaco, bed G 1219, 1557. All figures natural size

- 2-3 m above base bed G1109: *Bredyia* sp. (MLP 17049, 17051, 2, 4, 9), *Planammatoceras planinsigne* (MLP 17047, 17053), *Westermanniceras groeberi* (MLP 17055-6).

62 m dark-red, reddish-brown cross-bedded sandstones and mudstones with interbedded volcanics (Remoredo Formation).

2. Quebrada Remoredo

Some ammonites from four different levels of this section were mentioned and figured by Spalletti *et al.* (2012). The only important discrepancy with the present paper is in the supposed presence of upper Toarcian, which is discussed and discounted below.

This section was studied by Gulisano and Gutiérrez Pleimling and described by Riccardi & Westermann (1991a).

5 m light gray limestones (La Manga Formation).

15 m dark-gray shales and limestones (Lotena Formation).

Middle part bed G1140, with: with: *Araucanites stipanicici*, *A.* cf. *reyesi* (MLP 17013, 17014, 17015) *Euaspidoceras* sp. (MLP 17016), *Otosphinctes* sp. (MLP 17017), *Arisphinctes* sp. (MLP 17018). Perisphinctes-Araucanites Zone.

Basal level, bed G1139, with *Rehmannia patagoniensis* (MLP 17009, 10, 12). Patagoniensis Horizon.

c. 60 m yellowish-gray and greenish sandstones (Lajas Formation):

- At 25 m bed G1138 with *Eurycephalites* sp. (MLP 17007), *Neuquenicerases* cf. *steinmanni* (MLP 17008). Bodenbenderi Zone.

- Lower 10 m bed G1136 and loose material (G1137), with *Stehnocephalites gerthi* (MLP 16998, 17001, 17005, 6), *Xenocephalites* cf. *neuquensis* (MLP 17003). (?Steinmanni Zone). From this level probably came specimens identified as “*Stehnocephalites gerthi*” and “*Iniskinites crassus*” in Spalletti *et al.* (2012, fig. 6A and 6D-E).

- Base of Lajas Formation, unconformably on top of Los Molles Formation, bed G 1135 with *Stehnocephalites gerthi*. Uppermost Bathonian.

190 m Dark-gray shales and sandstones (Los Molles Formation). Several fossiliferous levels:

- At c. 170 m bed G 1132 with *Stephanoceras* (*Stemmatoceras*) cf. *allani* (MLP 16999). Humphriesianum Zone.

- At c. 145 m bed G1130 with *Doresetensia blancoensis* (MLP 16997), ?*Witchellia* sp. (MLP 17000). Giebeli Zone.

- At c. 135 m bed G1129 with *Dorsetensia blancoensis* (MLP 16991, 3, 5), *D. mendozai* (MLP 16989, 16990, 2, 4), Giebeli Zone.

- At c.132 m bed G1128 with *Dorsetensia* aff. *edouardiana* (MLP 16987), *Sonninia alsatica* (MLP 16986), Giebeli Zone.

- At c.130 m bed G1127 with *Emileia* cf. *multiformis* (MLP 16984).

- At c. 90-120 m beds G 1121, 2, 4,5, 6, mostly loose, with *Sonninia* cf. *espinazitensis* (MLP 16978, 16982, 4, 17692), *Emileia giebeli* (MLP 16977, 75, 16980), Giebeli Zone. *Sonninia altecostata* (MLP 16976, 16985), *Lytoceras* sp. (MLP 16988). Singularis Zone.

- At 100 m bed G1118 with *Sonninia altecostata* (MLP 16969) *Pseudotoites* cf. *sphaerocerooides* (MLP 16967, 71). Singularis Zone.

- At 50 m bed G 1116 with *Sonninia* (*Euhoploceras*) sp. (MLP 16974), *Puchenquia malarguensis*. (MLP 16968), ?*Fontannesia* sp. (MLP 16972). Malarguensis Zone.

- 38-46 m. From a level within this interval comes the specimen identified as “*Dumortieria* cf. *pusilla*” by Spalletti *et al.* (2012, figs 3A, 4B), which could well be a Sonniniidae.

- At c. 10 m bed G 1114 with *Planammatoceras* cf. *planinsigne* (MLP 16973). ?Groeberi Zone.

41 m whitish sandstones (Bardas Blancas Formation).

- At c. 18 m bed G1111 with *Bredyia* sp. (MLP 17020). Manflasensis Zone.

10 m upper part of a thick succession of dark-red, reddish-brown cross-bedded sandstones and mudstones with interbedded volcanics (Remoredo Formation).

3. Quebrada de la Buitrera

This section is located on the western slope of Sierra de Reyes, to the north of Quebrada Remoredo, and has been described previously by Groeber (1918, 1929, 1933), Groeber *et al.* (1953), Stipanovic (1966) and Riccardi & Westermann (1991a).

13 m fine to medium-grained brown to yellowish calcareous sandstones (Lajas Formation). Five meters below top, bed G1196, with *Neuquenicerases* sp.

Plate XI

Figs 1-2. *Stehnocephalites gerthi* (Stehn), incomplete phragmocone with distorted body chamber (MLP 17001), lateral and ventral views, Quebrada Remoredo, bed G1136-1137.

Figs 3-4. *Lilloettia steinmanni* (Spath), incomplete phragmocone (MLP 17086), lateral and ventral views, La Estrechura, bed G 1157.

Figs 5-6. *Neuquenicerases* cf. *steinmanni* Stehn, phragmocone with body chamber (MLP 17008). Ventral and lateral views, Quebrada Remoredo, bed G 1138.

All figures natural size

(MLP19436), Eurycephalitinae indet, (MLP 19435, 7, 8). 120 m dark and yellow gray shales and sandstones (Los Molles Formation), several fossiliferous levels:

- 10 m below top with bed G1188, *Megasphaeroceras* cf. *magnum* (MLP19433, 4; Pl. VII, figs 1-2). Rotundum Zone.
- 38-52 m below top, bed 1187 with *Dorsetensiamendozai* (MLP19419, 20, 24, 28, 29, 30), *D.* aff. *edouardiana* (MLP 19422, 3), *Dorsetensia* sp. (MLP 19426, 7, 31, 2), and bed G1186 with *Emileia* (*Chondromileia*) sp. (MLP 19417), *Sonninia* cf. *espinazitensis*, *S.* cf. *alsatica* (MLP 19418) and *Sonninia* sp. (MLP 19425). Giebeli Zone.
- 62 m below top bed G1185, with *Pseudotoites* sp. (MLP 19411), *Sonninia altecostata* (MLP 19414, 5, 6). Singularis Zone.
- 70 m below top bed G1184, with *S.* cf. *mirabilis* (MLP 19591).
- 72 m below top bed G1183 with *Sonninia* cf. *zitteli* (MLP19410). Singularis Zone.
- 80 m below top bed G1182 with *Sonninia* sp. (MLP 19413).
- 100 m below top bed G1181 with *Csernyeiceras moerickei* (MLP 19412) Malarguensis Zone.
- Base not visible.

4. Agua del Ñaco and Cañada Honda

The section at Agua del Ñaco was studied and collected by Gulisano in 1984 and described by Riccardi & Westermann (1991a, 1999). Immediately to the south it merges with Cañada Honda (4), with a similar section, which was described by Groeber (1933, p. 13; Groeber *et al.*, 1953). About 2 km to the north of Agua del Ñaco, another sections is exposed at Agua de Reyes (5).

200 m gypsum (Auquilco Formation).

6 m whitish-gray limestones (La Manga Formation).

15 m dark gray shales with interbedded limestones (Lotena Formation), bed G1562, with *Rehmannia patagoniensis* (MLP 20063, 4, 20065, 6, 7, 8, 9, 70, 1). Patagoniensis Horizon.

15 m yellow-gray and greenish sandstones (Lajas Formation).

15 m above base bed G 1563: ?*Eurycephalites* sp. (MLP 20074), *Choffatia* sp. (MLP 20072, 3).

3 m above base bed G1558 with: *Stehnocephalites gerthi* (MLP 20058, 9). Gerthi Horizon.

At base bed G1557, with: *Lilloettia steinmanni* (Spath) (MLP20053), *Iniskinites gulisanoi*, *Iniskinites* sp. nov. A, *Eurycephalites* sp. (MLP 20051, 4, 5, 6, 7; 20079, 80, 1, 2, 4), ?*Xenocephalites neuquensis* (MLP 20048), *Oxycerites* cf. *aspidoides* (MLP 20046, 9, 20050), ?*Oxycerites* sp. nov., *Procerites* cf. *schloenbachi* (MLP 20040, 20052), *Morphoceras gulisanoi* (MLP 20076, 8, 20041, 3, 4, 5, 20047). Steinmanni/Gulisanoi Zone.

14.5 m dark grey shales and mudstones (Los Molles Formation).

At base bed G1218 with: *Sphaeroceras* (*Defonticeras*) cf. *defontii* (MLP 20077), *Stephanoceras* sp. (MLP 20075). Humphriesianum Zone.

5. Agua de Reyes

This section is on the eastern slope of Sierra de Reyes, about 2 km north of Agua de Ñaco, and was studied by Groeber (1918, pp. 10-11; 1933, p. 11) and collected by R.A. Pombo in 1978 (Samples M) and by C. Gulisano and A. Gutiérrez Pleimling in 1984 (Samples G).

200 m gypsum (Auquilco Formation).

10 m whitish limestones (La Manga Formation), with a few fossiliferous levels (G1215-1217).

20 m limestones with interbedded sandstones and shales (Lotena Formation), near base beds M13, G1213 with *Rehmannia patagoniensis* (MLP 14047, 19578-82). Patagoniensis Horizon.

18 m cross bedded sandstones (Lajas Formation).

10 m shales (Los Molles Formation).

c. 232 m sandstones in c. 50 m of lower part with shales (Bardas Blancas Formation) Several fossiliferous levels?

- At 240 m bed G1209 with: *Emileia* sp. (MLP19488), *Stephanoceras* sp. (MLP 19487). Humphresianum Zone.
- At 230 m bed G1208 with: *Sonninia* (*Papilliceras*) *espinazitensis*, *Dorsetensia mendozai* (MLP19486). Giebeli Zone.
- At 205 m bed M12 with *Dorsetensia* sp. (MLP14046). Giebeli Zone.
- At 200 m bed G1207 with: *Dorsetensia mendozai* (MLP19484), *Dorsetensia* sp. (MLP 19483). Giebeli Zone.
- At 195 m bed M11 with *Emileia* (*Chondromileia*) *giebeli* (Gottsche) (MLP 10045). Giebeli Zone.
- At 185 m bed G1206 with: *Emileia multiformis* (MLP

Plate XII

Figs 1-2. *Rehmannia* (*Loczyceras*) *patagoniensis* (Weaver), incomplete phragmocone (MLP 23986), lateral and ventral views, Agua de la Mula, bed M 222.

Figs 3-4. *Perisphinctes* (*Dichotomoceras*) cf. *wartae* (Bukowski), incomplete phragmocone and body chamber (MLP 13346), lateral and ventral views, Agua de la Mula, bed M 228.

Fig. 5. *Euaspidoceras* aff. *waageni* Spath, complete specimen (MLP 13345, lateral view, Agua de la Mula, bed M 239).

All figures natural size

- 20085, 6, 7, 8) *Sonninia (Papilliceras) espinazitensis* (MLP 20089, 91, 92), *Dorsetensia mendozai* (MLP 20090), Giebeli Zone.
- At 170 m bed M10 with *Sonninia altecostata* (MLP 14044).
 - At 160 m bed G1205 with *Emileia multiformis* (MLP 19485) *Emileia* sp., *Sonninia (Papilliceras) espinazitensis*. Giebeli Zone.
 - At 155 m, beds M9, G1204 with: *Sonninia altecostata* (MLP 14043, 4, 19479), *Sonninia zitteli* (MLP 19482). Singularis Zone.
 - At c. 125 m bed M8 with *Sonniniidae* indet (MLP14042).
 - At 115 m bed M7 with *Puchenquia* cf. *malarguensis* (Burck.).(MLP14041). Malarguensis Zone.
 - At 85 m bed G1203 with: *Sonninia (Euhoploceras) amosi* (MLP 19480). Malarguensis Zone.
 - At 70 m bed M6, with: *Ammonitina* indet.
 - At 30 m beds M3, G1201 with: *Tmetoceras* cf. *scissum* (M3, MLP 14039, G1201, MLP 19481). Malarguensis/Groeberi Zone.
 - At 5 m bed M1 with: *?Planammatoceras* sp. (MLP14038).

6. Agua de la Mula

This section, on the southeastern slope of Sierra de Reyes, slightly to the north of Agua de Reyes, was studied and collected by M. Uliana, A. Riccardi, S. Damborenea and M. Manceñido in 1973 and described by Riccardi & Westermann (1991a). About 4.5 km to the north another section described by Groeber *et al.* (1953, pp. 204-205) is exposed at Agua del Campo (8). At Agua de la Mula the fossiliferous succession is as follows (numbers of fossil samples as in Fig. 1):

+ 100 m gypsum, lower part of the Auquilco Formation.
8.5 m light-gray limestones (La Manga Formation) beds M224-227 with: *Araucanites mulai* (MLP 12247), *A. reyesi* (MLP 12241, 2, 3), *A.* sp. nov. (MLP 12246), *?Euspidoceras* aff. *wageni* Spath (MLP 13345) and *Arisphinctes* sp. (MLP 12857). *Perisphinctes* – *Araucanites* Zone.

15 m dark gray shales with interbedded limestones (Lotena Formation), close to base with *Rehmannia patagoniensis* (M222, MLP 23984-5). *R. patagoniensis* Horizon.

c. 150 m yellow-gray and greenish sandstones (Bardas Blancas Formation), with several fossiliferous levels:

- At c. 130 above base bed M221 with *Stephanoceras* cf. *pyritosum* (Quenstedt) (MLP 12855). Humphriesianum Zone.
- At 105 m above base bed M220 with *?Stephanoceras* sp. (MLP 12854).
- At 102 m above base bed M219 with *Sonninia* cf. *espinazitensis* and *Emileia* cf. *multiformis* (MLP 12853), Giebeli Zone.
- At 80 m above base bed M218 with *Sonninia* cf. *altecostata* (MLP 12852).
- At 75 m above base with *Sonninia* sp. (A).
- At 70 m above base bed M 217 with *Sonninia* cf. *altecostata*, (MLP 123851) and *Pseudotoites* sp. (MLP12856, 12858). Singularis Zone.

c. 10 m dark grey shales and mudstones (Los Molles Formation).

Close to top: bed M213 with *Podagrosiceras athleticum* Maub. & Lamb. (MLP 12817).

Close to base bed M212 with *Tmetoceras scissum* (MLP 10993). Malarguensis/Groeberi Zone.

10 m Upper part of a succession 40 m thick of dark-red, reddish-brown cross-bedded sandstones and mudstones with interbedded volcanics and conglomerates (Remoredo Formation).

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Plate XIII

- Fig. 1. *Euspidoceras* aff. *wageni* Spath, complete specimen (MLP 13345, apertural view, Agua de la Mula, bed M227.
Figs 2-3. *Arisphinctes* sp., incomplete phragmocone (MLP 17018), lateral and ventral views, Quebrada Remoredo, bed G1140.
Figs 4-5. *Araucanites stipanicici* Westermann & Riccardi, almost complete specimen (MLP 12240), lateral and ventral views, Agua de Reyes, bed G1213.
All figures natural size

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